

ҲАРБИЙЛАШГАН ТАЪЛИМ КУРСАНТЛАРИГА ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИШДА КОММУНИКАТИВ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШДА АКТНИНГ ЎРНИ

Дадабаева Ҳаётхон Фахридин қизи

ЎзДЖТУ 2-инглиз тили факультети Мактабгача ва бошланғич таълимда

Инглиз тили йўналиши

2-босқич талабаси

Илмий раҳбар: Тешабаева Дилфуза Муминовна

Аннотация: Мақолада ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан ҳарбийлашган таълим муассасаларидаги бўлажак офицерларига хорижий тилларнинг коммуникатив малакасини эгаллашга ёрдам бериш воситаси сифатида фойдаланиш таҳлили, назарий асослари ва эмпирик синов натижалари келтирилган. Тил ўргатишда қўлланиладиган АКТнинг кенг қўлами ҳамда курсантларнинг тил ўрганиш жараёнига АКТни интегратсиялашувининг мантиқий асослари келтирилди. Ҳарбий ўқув муҳитида АКТ самарадорлигини текшириш мақсадида педагогик тажриба ўтказилди; унинг топилмалари тасвирланган. Ҳарбий олий таълим муассасасида тил ўрганиш жараёнида АКТдан фойдаланиш самарадорлигини исботлади, натижада курсантларнинг тил билиши, касбий тайёргарлиги ва умумий академик кўникмалари. АКТни татбиқ этиш курсантларнинг тил ўрганишга бўлган муносабатига таъсир кўрсатувчи кучли мотиватсияни таъминлашда ва уларнинг мустақиллиги, ижодий ва когнитив қобилиятларини ривожлантиришда муҳим рол ойнади. Бўлажак офицерлар она тилида сўзлашувчилар, ҳамкасблари ёки ҳарбий экспертлар билан ўзаро алоқа қилиш ва ҳақиқий алоқани сақлаб қолиш, видео чатлар ва видео кўнғироқлар орқали халқаро лойиҳаларда иштирок этиш қобилиятини айниқса илҳомлантирувчи ва ёқимли тажриба деб топдилар. АКТни интегратсиялашнинг яна бир афзаллиги курсантларнинг индивидуал таълим услубига қараб мавзунини турли йўллар билан тақдим этиш имкониятидир. Расм, видео, мултимедиа тақдимоти, инфографика каби кўргазмаларни қурооллардан фойдаланиш курсантларни ўқишга қизиқтирди, расмлар, графикалар, иллюстратсиялар, аудио ва видеолар билан тасвирланганда матнларни тушунишни осонлаштиради. Технология курсантларга ўқиш жараёни устидан кўпроқ назорат ва синфда ҳамкорлик қилиш учун кўпроқ эркинлик берди.

Калит сўзлар: ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари (АКТ); курсантлар; чет тилининг коммуникатив компетенсияси; тил ўрганиш.

Аннотация: В статье представлены анализ, теоретические основы и результаты эмпирической апробации использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий как средства помощи будущим офицерам в военно-учебных заведениях в овладении коммуникативной компетенцией на иностранных языках. Был представлен широкий спектр ИКТ, используемых в обучении языку, и обоснование интеграции ИКТ в процесс изучения языка слушателями. Проведен педагогический эксперимент с целью проверки эффективности ИКТ в военно-образовательной среде; описаны его находки. Доказана эффективность использования ИКТ в процессе обучения языку в военном вузе, в результате чего улучшаются языковые навыки, профессиональная подготовка и общеучебные навыки курсантов. Внедрение ИКТ сыграло важную роль в обеспечении сильной мотивации, влияющей на отношение учащихся к изучению языка и в развитии их независимости, творчества и когнитивных навыков. Будущие офицеры нашли возможность взаимодействовать и поддерживать реальный контакт с носителями языка, коллегами или военными экспертами, а также участвовать в международных проектах посредством видеочатов и видеозвонков, что особенно вдохновляет и доставляет удовольствие. Еще одним преимуществом интеграции ИКТ является возможность представить предмет по-разному, в зависимости от индивидуального стиля обучения обучаемых. Использование наглядных пособий, таких как картинки, видео, мультимедийные презентации, инфографика, вызвало у студентов интерес к чтению и облегчило понимание текстов, когда они были проиллюстрированы картинками, графикой, иллюстрациями, аудио и видео. Технологии дали учащимся больше контроля над своим обучением и больше свободы для совместной работы в классе.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ); курсанты; коммуникативная компетенция иностранного языка; изучение языка.

Annotation: The article presents the analysis, theoretical foundations, and results of empirical testing of the use of information and communication technologies as a means of helping future officers in military educational institutions master communicative competence in foreign languages. A wide range of ICTs used in language teaching was presented, and the rationale for integrating ICTs into the process

of language learning by students was presented. Conducted a pedagogical experiment to test the effectiveness of ICT in the military educational environment; his finds are described. The effectiveness of the use of ICT in the process of teaching a language in a military university has been proven, as a result of which language skills, professional training, and general education skills of cadets are improved. The introduction of ICT has played an important role in providing strong motivation influencing students' attitudes towards language learning and in developing their independence, creativity, and cognitive skills. Future officers have found the opportunity to interact and maintain real contact with native speakers, colleagues, or military experts, as well as to participate in international projects through video chats and video calls, which are especially inspiring and enjoyable. Another advantage of integrating ICT is the ability to present the subject in different ways, depending on the individual learning style of the trainees. The use of visual aids such as pictures, videos, multimedia presentations, and infographics aroused students' interest in reading and made texts easier to understand when they were illustrated with pictures, graphics, illustrations, audio, and video. Technology has given students more control over their learning and more freedom to collaborate in the classroom.

Keywords: information and communication technologies (ICT); cadets; communicative competence of a foreign language; language learning.

The system of joining into the Asian and worldwide military local area picked by the Uzbek state completes the issue of interoperability of the Uzbek armed force with the military of different nations, which, thusly, prompts the need to expand the degree of foreign language skill of Uzbekistan's tactical faculty. At present, viable foreign language learning is unimaginable without the utilization of data and correspondence innovations (ICT), as they give admittance to expansive instructive data assets to further develop foreign language relational abilities, update basic and imaginative reasoning, draw in trainees in many open undertakings, and raise their inspiration and language mindfulness. The adequacy of consolidating creative techniques for educating/learning English with the utilization of ICT is stretching out the potential open doors for recruits to obtain open capability rehearsing English with genuine individuals and in genuine settings; which is attainable by empowering and driving them to utilize innovation for their potential benefit [1.16].

Choosing legitimate and productive showing strategies, structures, methodologies, and procedures is a key to future officials' obtaining compelling

informative capability. Innovation extraordinarily affects showing English, as it makes instructors reexamine what they are doing and extend the number of training ways to deal with expanding educational experience and make it more useful. The utilization of ICT can make the learning climate adaptable, intuitive, and creative. "The monstrous improvement of data advances causes large changes additionally in a training process", guarantee S. Hubackova and M. Ruzickova. As indicated by the definition by Asabere and Enguah, ICT are the offices, devices, supplies, and cycles that furnish the required climate with the foundation and administrations for the aggregation, handling, putting away, transmission, and spread of data including text, voice, information, video, and designs. Among the ICT are intelligent whiteboards, PCs, office applications (Word, PowerPoint, drawing instruments, and so on), PC-helped language learning (CALL) and Language board Frameworks (LMS) programming, the Web - sites and downloadable programming, course books Disc ROMs, blue ray players, cell phones, electronic word references, computerized cameras and recordings, DAT recorders, archive cameras, information projectors [2.43].

Along these lines, Livingstone states that ICT incorporates innovations intended for the learning climate (for example intuitive whiteboards) and organized innovations. Hennessy contends that the term ICT envelops a scope of equipment (work area and versatile PCs, projection innovation, computerized recording gear, information logging), programming (nonexclusive programming, mixed media assets), and method for telecom and data frameworks (Intranet, Web). ICT alludes to innovative apparatuses and assets which are utilized to convey, make, scatter and oversee data. D. That's what çakici trusts "the increment of data and correspondence innovations has emphatically supported and made strong learning climate". Without uncertainty, ICT is viewed as fundamental in language preparation for the military, since it can be consolidated at different phases of the instructive process, guaranteeing a singular methodology (beginning from symptomatic testing and as far as possible up to individual undertakings recruits need to achieve on PCs during their graduation tests), expanding trainees' inspiration to work on their open and language capability using different programming and Web assets, giving a persistent evaluation of recruits' degree of open abilities and capacities, and checking their headway through different data resources, making language climate inventive, adaptable, and intuitive [3.110]. Among the immense range of ICT, sight and sound advancements and instructive programming are maybe the most well-known and generally utilized in the language classroom today.

We can't however impart the insight of I. A. Vereitina, who expresses that to be instrumental in shaping foreign language skills, ICT is to be utilized in a particular instructive climate which needs to:

- guarantee intelligent types of learning;
- be misleadingly established to give PC a coordinated climate;
- offer educational help conveyed information;
- kill students' physiological protection from learning in a virtual climate;
- empower students' singular examinations in the virtual area.

The advancement of the expression "open ability" begins with D. Hymes, who characterized it as a part of one's ability that empowers the individual to arrange implications relationally inside unambiguous settings. Zero in is placed on the capacity to impart practically and intelligently in a language. Securing informative capability includes the development of a specific arrangement of language abilities, in particular: the capacity to obviously and soundly express oneself in a foreign language; the capacity to portray some current, past, future, or theoretical circumstance, delivering related feelings and sentiments, plans and assumptions; capacity to talk easily and immediately, without a substantial need to pick words in a foreign language; capacity to successfully involve a foreign language in friendly correspondences and viewpoint proficient exercises, capacity to find, collect, store, send, change, and scatter data in a foreign language with the assistance of data and specialized devices; capacity to communicate one's thoughts thoroughly, exhaustively and consistently through different syntactic means; capacity to intercede in a foreign language; and the capacity to complete right interpretation of expertly arranged texts [4.56].

Future officers of the Uzbek military during the time spent their language learning are supposed to frame open capability which is cooperative energy of informative information, abilities, and capacities. To accomplish this, educators need to carefully choose or foster a bunch of exercises that can be carried out utilizing data and correspondence innovations to upgrade open (tuning in, perusing, varying media discernment) and useful (talking and composing) spaces of language skill. The review included a bunch of examination strategies that meet its objectives and targets, in particular: hypothetical: the examination of philosophical, humanistic, mental, educational, verifiable, and strategic assets to validate the hypothetical and systemic groundworks of the issue under study; systematization and speculation of the

experience of involving current ICT during the time spent language instructing/learning; reflection, romanticizing, logical structural investigation of the explored issue; exact: educational trial to recognize the viability of the utilization of ICT in line of open capability of future safeguard experts; poll, overview, testing, examination of recruits' presentation of imaginative assignments to decide the degree of marks of open skill; master evaluation of structures, strategies, method for arrangement of open ability of future officials and the job of ICT during the time spent language preparing; measurable: techniques for numerical measurements to check the dependability and meaning of the consequences of the led explore (Fisher's angular change basis) [5.90].

Conclusion. The way that ICT supports current standards of learning and language obtaining is undoubtful. They assist with making a student-focused, intuitive, all-around planned, and adaptable learning climate. The review demonstrates that utilizing ICT is most certainly instrumental in shaping the open capability of future armed force officials by giving strong inspiration, and advancing their independence, imagination, and mental abilities. The reasoning behind coordinating ICT in the language classroom is to empower recruits to work with exceptional and credible sources, work with collaboration, and give more noteworthy opportunities and adaptability to learn at one's speed and comfort. The experience of utilizing innovation to supplement customary English classes has ended up being positive and animating both for recruits and instructors, giving them genuine contact with, and openness to encounters with local speakers and empowering future officials to access and research required data around the world [6.157].

The accessibility and legitimate utilization of sources like CALL and LMS programming, sound and video cuts, pictures, activities, e-word references, applications, PowerPoint introductions, and so forth were seen as extremely rousing, as they support recruits rehearsing a language another way. It has been laid out that utilizing PC innovation as a device in language showing builds recruits' certainty, proficient readiness, language capability, and generally scholarly abilities. In the illumination of the previously mentioned, it very well may be reasoned that fostering trainees' open skill utilizing different ICT is compelling, as it yields unmistakable results, adjusts to the present-day necessities of the instructive cycle, and addresses recruits' issues. Also, this approach can be utilized both in the classroom and during self-study, giving more opportunity and adaptability to learn at one's speed and

accommodation [7.256]. Concerning the possibilities for additional examination, our idea is that unmistakable strategic rules as well as viable proposals ought to be created on the most proficient method to have a great cluster of ICT devices completely integrated into the unknown dialect educational experience to work with a learning climate that will open additional opportunities.

REFERENCES

1. S. Hennessy, K. Ruthven, and S. Brindley, *Teacher perspectives on integrating ICT into subject teaching: Commitment, constraints, caution and change*, 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://www.educ.cam.ac.uk/research/projects/istl/WP042.pdf>. Accessed on: March 7, 2021. p 16.
2. M. Yunus, N. Nordin, H. Salehi, C. H. Sun, and M. A. Embi, "Pros and cons of using ICT in teaching ESL reading and writing, *International Education Studies*, vol. 6, no. 7, 2013. p 43.
3. V. Yu. Bykov, "Theoretical and methodological principles of creating and developing modern means and technologies of learning", *Collection of scientific works marking 10 years of Pedagogical Sciences Academy existence*, vol. 2, 2002. pp. 110-125.
4. R. S. Gurevych, I. A. Shakhina, and A. O. Podzygun, "Google classroom as an effective tool of smart learning and monitoring of students' knowledge in vocational schools", *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, vol. 79, no. 5, 2020. p 56.
5. M. I. Zhaldak, V. Yu. Bykov, and O. Yu. Burov, *Theoretical and methodological principles of education informatization and practical realization of information and communication technologies in the educational sphere in Ukraine*. Kyiv: Komprynt, 2019. pp. 86-114.
6. I. Ye. Klak, and N. I. Yatseniuk, "Forming the prospective foreign language teachers' communicative competence by means of multimedia teaching technologies", *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, vol. 76, no. 2, 2020. p 157.
7. A. Yu. Yurzhenko, "An e-course based on the LMS MOODLE to teach maritime English for professional purpose", *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, vol. 71, no. 3, 2019. p 256.

8. S. Hubackova and M. Ruzickova, “Experience in foreign language teaching with ICT support”, *Procedia Computer Science*, Vol. 56, no 3, 2011. p 8.
9. N. Y. Asabere, and S. E. Enguah, “Integration of expert systems in mobile learning”, *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Research*, vol. 2, no.1, 2012. p 14.
10. S. Livingstone, “Critical reflections on the benefits of ICT in education”, *Oxford Review of Education*, vol. 38, no. 1, 2012. p 21.
11. D. Çakici, “The use of ICT in teaching English as a foreign language”, *Participatory Educational Research*, no 4, 2016. pp 3-9.
12. I. A. Vereitina, “Virtuality in an educational environment”, *Higher education*, no. 3, 2012. p 47.
13. D. H. Hymes, *On Communicative Competence*, Sociolinguistics. Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1972. p 103.
14. B. H. Spitzberg and W. R. Cupach, *Inter Personal Communication Competence*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage, 2012. p 52.
15. B. Ghasemi and M. Hashemi, “ICT: New wave in English language learning/teaching”, *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 56, no 3, 2011. p 67.

